

On the Soundness of Auto-Completion Services for Dynamically Typed Languages (Python test set)

1 Python test set

This section displays all programs as used in our experiment. For every program, the ? indicates the cursor position from where an auto-completion request is executed.

1.1 *self-ref*

The *self-ref* program is given by the following snippet.

```
x = 2
x1 = x?
```

The rationale behind this program is that when assigning to x1, x1 itself is not in scope. Thus, only x is a valid completion candidate at the cursor position.

1.2 *if-else1*

The *if-else1* program is given by the following snippet.

```
x = 0
if x:
    x2 = 0
else:
    x3 = 0
```

```
print(x?)
```

The rationale behind this program is that the condition is always false, so the assignment to x2 is never executed, and the assignment to x3 is always executed. As a result, x and x3 are sound completion candidates at the cursor position.

1.3 *if-else2*

The *if-else2* program is given by the following snippet.

```
x = input()
if x:
    x2 = 0
else:
    x3 = 0
```

```
print(x?)
```

This is a variant of the previous program where we do not know until run-time whether the condition evaluates to true or false. As a result, only x is a valid completion at the cursor position.

1.4 *if-else3*

The *if-else3* program is given by the following snippet.

```
x = 0
if x:
    x2 = 0
```

```
else:
    x3 = 0
    print(x?)
```

In this program, we perform the query inside the body of the else. From that point, the x3 variable and the x variable are always in scope, and thus sound completion candidates. The x2 variable is never in scope, and thus an unsound completion candidate.

1.5 *if-else-both*

The *if-else-both* program is given by the following snippet.

```
x = 0
if x:
    x2 = 0
else:
    x3 = 0
```

```
x = 1
if x:
    x2 = 0
else:
    x3 = 0
```

```
print(x?)
```

This program repeats the *if-else1* program, but executes both branches by repeating the if-else statement and changing the value x before the second branch. As a result, both branches are executed and at the completion point all three variables are definitely in scope.

1.6 *duck-type*

The *duck-type* program is given by the following snippet.

```
class x1:
    x11 = 0
    x = 1
```

```
class x2:
    x21 = 0
    x = 1
```

```
if input():
    b = x1()
else:
    b = x2()
```

```
print(b.x?)
```

This program features the well known duck-typing feature. In the example, the variable `b` can be assigned an instance from class `x1` or from `x2`, dependent on the result of the conditional. The two classes only share the `x` field. Thus, if we auto-complete at the cursor position, only `x` is a sound candidate, since it is present in both classes.

1.7 *use-before-define*

The *use-before-define* program is given by the following snippet.

```
x = 2

print(x?)

xAfter = 1
```

In Python, the available variables depends on the location of a completion request. In this example, we perform the completion request before the definition of the `xAfter` variable. As a result, it is not in scope and only `x` is a sound completion candidate.

1.8 *use-before-define-fn*

The *use-before-define-fn* program is given by the following snippet.

```
def x():
    print(x?)

x()

def xAfter():
    pass
```

This program is a slight variant of the previous program, where the definitions are functions. Again, the same principle holds, the variables in scope inside the `x` function depend on where `x` is called. In this example, the `x` function is called before the definition of the `xAfter` function. Therefore, `xAfter` is not in scope when the body of `x` is executed, and hence only `x` itself is a valid completion candidate.

2 *add-field*

The *add-field* program is given by the following snippet.

```
class B:
    x = 2

def addField(x):
    x.x1 = 2

b = B()
addField(b)

print(b.x?)
```

The Python programming language allows objects to be extended at run-time by adding new fields or methods. The available completion when completing an object access, can thus depend on possible modifications to the object. In this example, the variable `b` is assigned an instance of the class `B`. After, the `addField` function is called, which adds the field `x1` to the object passed to the function. After this call, the instance assigned to the `b` variable thus has two fields: `x` and `x1`. Both these fields are sound auto-completions at the cursor position in the example.

2.1 *not-called-fn*

The *not-called-fn* program is given by the following snippet.

```
def notcalled():
    x = 1
    x1 = 2
    print(x?)
```

This program contains a function that is not actually called from the file in which it is defined, simulating a library function.

2.2 *obj-param*

The *obj-param* program is given by the following snippet.

```
class A:
    x1 = 2
    x2 = 3

class B:
    x1 = 2
    x3 = 3

def objParam(o):
    print(o.x?)

a = A()
b = B()

objParam(a)
objParam(b)
```

This program captures the idea that the completion candidates of function parameters depend on the arguments passed to these functions. In this example, we pass two objects of two different classes to the `objParam` function. When auto-completing the `o` parameter in the `objParam`, we can only give suggestions that are present on both objects. If we give a suggestion that is only present on one object, one of the function calls will crash. Hence, only `x1` is a valid completion candidate at the cursor position.

2.3 *global-add*

The *global-add* program is given by the following snippet.

```
x = 1

def addGlobal():
    global xx
    xx = 2

addGlobal()

print(x?)
```

This program includes the `global` construct, which enables the addition of a variable to the global scope. In this example, `xx` is thus defined at the global scope and not inside the scope of the `addGlobal` function. As a result, both `x` and `xx` are sound completion candidates at the cursor position.

2.4 *not-global-add*

The addition of `xx` to the global scope in the previous program, depends on the function `addGlobal` being called. In the *not-global-add* program, we have the same program without the call to `addGlobal`. As a result, `xx` is never added to the global scope, and only `x` is a sound completion candidate at the cursor position.

```
x = 1

def addglobal():
    global xx
    xx = 2

print(x?)
```